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Language interaction and mediation as a special type of speech activity

In our time, preparing students as highly qualified specialists holds significant importance in the field of education. In teaching English to students, communicative competence occupies an important place. Analysis of scientific-pedagogical literature on effective education has shown that this method helps in shaping students' professional skills and developing their personal virtues.

The establishment of the system is related to the increase in the number of people coming to Europe in search of work. In the mid-20th century, as production began to develop in Europe and new jobs were created, the demand for more labor increased, and the number of people coming to Europe in search of work and intending to settle there permanently grew. At that time, in addition to Spanish, German, French, and Italian, English was also widely used in Europe. Those coming to Europe to settle needed to be able to communicate easily and without problems with the local population. Therefore, those coming to work in Europe had to pass special exams. Although exams based on the CEFR system were initially taken for all languages spoken in Europe, today the CEFR system is most commonly used for teaching, learning, and assessing English. This is because the whole world is speaking English, and it has become the number one global language.

The CEFR (Common European Framework of Reference for Languages) system encompasses issues related to the learning, teaching, and assessment of languages used throughout Europe. As a result of globalization and modern technological means that facilitate easy communication among people, the CEFR system is widely applied not only in Europe but also in other countries such as Colombia and the Philippines. In Uzbekistan, following the President's decree in 2012, the demand for learning and teaching English significantly increased, and as a result, the new national NSFLA system was established based on the CEFR.

This article examines the boundaries of communicative competence through a modern approach and looks at innovations in methodological aspects of developing interaction skills. The expansion of the concept of "communicative competence" arises due to a new component - multilingualism and multicultural competence. The

problems of the interactive educational process and its scientific foundations determine the essence of this article. Moreover, the basis of the article is the new theory as the scientific foundation of interactive interaction for developing an individual's creative activity in an innovative social and cultural environment during the study of the English language. The concept of interaction (in English - interaction) has a long history in science. However, even today, the role of methodological interaction in education encourages us to analyze interaction more broadly. During the learning process, there is a need to define the unique characteristics of these concepts for more rigorous use during an interactive lesson. One of the important aspects is that the successful application of numerous interactive technologies requires an understanding of the foundations and principles of methodological collaboration, knowledge of its history, modern characteristics of interaction, and the regulatory requirements for its orderly application. The recently developed theoretical approaches and technologies (pedagogical or methodological) for person-centered education are more suited to the tasks of developing an individual's creative activity during the interaction process. However, in our opinion, the entropy factor of students' and teachers' consciousness is not fully taken into account in these scientific and practical directions during the constant humanitarian crisis. A.A. Kolesnikov and O.G. Polyakov proposed an integrated model of "Intercultural Communicative Competence" for foreign languages. It includes, as a necessary condition in the intercultural context, special types of interaction and mediation speech activities that encompass bilingual social and multicultural knowledge as part of verbal and non-verbal behaviors. The last decades have been marked by the final affirmation of the anthropocentric paradigm in foreign language teaching, which implies the priority of a personal approach in the processes of self-identification and in considering competencies during their formation. Strengthening individualization, learning, and planning and implementing an individual educational direction in the process of learning a foreign language (self-learning) increases the student's responsibility. Analyzing and substantiating the personality of each person involved in the educational process has become the starting point.

According to Vera Petrovna Samarina's article "INNOVATIVE PRODUCTIVE METHOD OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES" from 2021: Vera Petrovna Samarina, Doctor of Economics, Professor, states that it is necessary to implement

an effective method in the educational process related to the problem of developing students' communicative competence in foreign languages.

The main methodological directions in this field of education are:

Formation of communicative competence;

Mastery of professional language competence;

Development of students' personal virtues. In this regard, speech competence is closely related to information communication.

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